

REVIEW: A RIGOROUS STUDY OF PLAIN AND NANOVESICLES GEL FORMULATIONS FOR TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY

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Abstract:

The search for innovative drug delivery methods improved effectiveness and customized therapeutic activity at the site of the body. As a possible carrier with enhanced skin penetration, invasomes are liposomal vesicles that contain trace amounts of ethanol plus terpenes or terpene combinations. When it comes to skin penetration, invasomes outperform liposomes and ethosomes. Invasomes offer several benefits, such as increasing patient comfort, compliance, and medication efficacy. Compared to traditional gels, invasomes, a unique vesicular technology, show better transdermal medication penetration through the skin. The present work focuses on a comparative study of conventional gel and invasomal gels for future aspects to highlight the numerous prospects of invasomal gel including their advantages, disadvantages, application, methods of preparation, and mechanism shown in diagrammatic representation.

Key words: Nano vesicles, Plain gel and Trans dermal drug delivery system.

Introduction:

A Novel Drug Delivery System (NDDS) refers to an advanced method of administering medications in a controlled and targeted manner to achieve optimal therapeutic outcomes. Unlike conventional dosage forms, NDDS is designed to deliver drugs at a specific rate, time and site within the body, thereby increasing efficacy and minimizing adverse effects. By utilizing innovative carriers such as liposomes, invasomes, microspheres, dendrimers and hydrogels, these systems enhance drug stability, improve bioavailability, and promote better patient adherence to treatment.

An invasomal gel is a novel topical or transdermal drug delivery system in which the drug is encapsulated within invasomes and incorporated into a suitable gel base for

application on the skin. Invasomes are elastic lipid vesicles composed of phospholipids, ethanol and terpenes, which work synergistically to enhance skin penetration. Ethanol fluidizes the lipid structure of the stratum corneum, while terpenes act as natural penetration enhancers. Due to their ultra-deformable nature, invasomes can easily pass through the skin barrier and deliver the drug into deeper skin layers or systemic circulation. Incorporation of invasomes into a gel improves formulation stability, ease of application, prolonged contact time with the skin and patient compliance. Overall, invasomal gels provide enhanced drug permeation, controlled drug release and improved therapeutic efficacy compared to conventional gels.⁽¹⁾

Figure : 1 Family of Novel Drug Delivery System

Advantages of Invasomal gels:

- Bypasses the skin's natural barriers to improve drug delivery.
- Allows for targeted delivery, reducing systemic exposure and side effects.
- Offers a painless alternative to injections, making patients more likely to follow through.
- Can deliver both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs.
- Contains non-toxic raw materials in the formulation.
- The ability to target particular tissues.

Disadvantages of Invasomal gels:

- More difficult to scale up and plan.
- Usually more costly to manufacture.
- The high expense of production ⁽²⁾.

Structure and Composition of Invasomes:

Small amounts of ethanol and other terpenes or terpene combinations are present in the soft liposomal vesicles called invasomes, which may function as carriers with enhanced skin penetration. They consist of water, a small amount of ethanol, terpenoids (including citral, limonene, and cineole), phospholipids and a small bit of alcohol⁽³⁾.

Figure : 2 Composition of Invasomes

Effect of Ethanol:

An efficient method to improve the fluidity of the skin's lipid bilayer is to incorporate ethanol into the formulation of lipid nanovesicles^(4,5). Ethanol's interaction with the lipid components in the SC's polar group area causes changes in the keratinized or lipophilic domains' structure, a drop in the lipids' transition temperature and ultimately fluidization and disruption of the tightly packed SC lipids^(6,7). The SC lipids can be fluidized and disturbed by ethanol-based nanocarriers⁽⁸⁾. Because the lipid acyl chains can rotate freely when ethanol is present, the intercellular lipid matrix becomes more flexible. As a result, ethanol makes the lipids in the vesicle structure more fluid, making it softer and less rigid than traditional liposomes⁽⁹⁾. In addition to improving penetration, ethanol limits vesicle aggregation through electrostatic repulsion and produces a net negative surface charge, which increases invasome stability during storage^(10, 11-13).

Effect of Terpenes:

Terpenes increase drug penetration by breaking up the tight bilayers and lipid packing in the SC, according to results from X-ray diffraction and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)⁽¹⁴⁾. Terpenes have also been shown to increase drug permeability through breaking hydrogen bonds and extracting SC lipids⁽¹⁵⁾, improving partition into the SC by improving lipid fluidity⁽¹⁶⁾ and increasing diffusion via intercellular lipids⁽¹⁷⁾. (**Dragicevic-Curic, N .et,al 2008**) showed that different terpene types have a synergistic effect on temoporfin penetration. The extent of temoporfin permeation was found to be directly influenced by both the concentration and diversity of terpenes incorporated into invasomes.

Formulations containing a 1% blend of citral, cineole and limonene exhibited superior permeation compared with invasomes containing 1% citral alone⁽¹⁸⁾, suggesting that the combined action of different terpenes enhances skin penetration more effectively than a single terpene. They found that temoporfin penetration is 1.7 times higher in vesicles with 1% terpenes than in vesicles with 0.5% terpenes. Thus deeper penetration may result from adding temoporfin to vesicles containing 1% terpenes . Terpene's Impact on Invasome particle size analysis showed that there is a direct relationship between the size of the invasomes and the quantity of terpenes; the invasomes get bigger as the terpene content rises. Vesicles with 1% terpenes were 124 nm in size, while those with 0.5% terpenes were 93.0 nm⁽¹⁰⁾. The molecular size of the terpene and the concentration of the added terpene affected the size of finasteride-loaded Invasomes. Invasomes containing nerolidol (molecular size 222 g/mol) ranged in size from 11 to 13 mm is told in **Prasanthi, D et,al** 2013.^(19,20).

Effect of Phospholipids:

Phospholipids are crucial in invasomes, acting as the basic structural component alongside ethanol and terpenes, providing flexibility and enhanced fluidity to the vesicle membrane, which allows them to deform, disrupt the skin's lipid barrier and deeply penetrate the skin for improved drug delivery, essentially making them superior to traditional liposomes for topical treatments.

Gel Penetration

Invasomal Gel Penetration

Table : 1 Penetration mechanism between Plain gel and invasomal gels

General Gel Penetration	Invasomal Gel Penetration
<p>Substances mostly enter the skin through a gradual process known as passive diffusion in a general gel formulation (left side of the image). The stratum corneum, the skin's outermost layer, has a tight structure that serves as a major barrier, restricting the</p>	<p>Invasomal Gels are Specifically made to get past this skin barrier, invasomes (right side of the image) provide better delivery and deeper penetration into the layers of the skin. "Elastic Vesicles + Penetration Enhancers" is how the image text describes invasomes. Phospholipids,</p>

Various Methods for Invasomes Preparation:

Invasomes are produced using a range of methods, each of which offers special advantages in terms of vesicle size, encapsulation efficiency, and scalability. The optimal strategy depends on the specific requirements of the drug and the desired characteristics of the invasomal formulation. Here, we look at some common techniques for Invasome preparation ⁽²¹⁾.

Thin Film Hydration: By dissolving lipid components in an organic solvent, this method produces a thin lipid coating on the container's surface. After the medication and surfactants are added to the film's aqueous phase, invasomes naturally form. Thin film hydration is a popular, versatile technique that is well known for being simple and scalable⁽²²⁾

Mechanical dispersion method: Invasomes are prepared by dissolving the drug along with individual terpenes or terpene mixtures in an ethanolic phospholipid solution. The resulting mixture is vortex-mixed for about 5 minutes, followed by sonication for another 5 minutes to obtain a clear and homogeneous solution. Subsequently, phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) is gradually added using a syringe under continuous vortexing. Vortexing is further continued for an additional 5 minutes to obtain the final invasomal formulation

Reverse Phase Evaporation: This method produces a water in oil (W/O) emulsion by dissolving lipids and the aqueous phase in an organic solvent. Invasomes are then produced by allowing the emulsion to evaporate. Reverse phase evaporation can be used to encapsulate hydrophilic drugs with high entrapment efficiencies.

Ether Injection Method: Lipids are dissolved in diethyl ether, and the organic phase is then added to an aqueous solution. Spontaneous vesicle formation results from the organic solvent's quick diffusion into the aqueous phase. This method is known to produce invasomes with small particle sizes and good drug encapsulation.

Freeze Drying Method: Invasomes prepared using this technique are freeze-dried to improve their stability and extend their shelf life. This method is effective for long-term storage and controlled drug release since the freeze-dried invasomes can be rehydrated before to distribution ⁽²³⁾.

Formulation of gel preparation:

The choice of vehicle/solvent: Normally purified water is used as a solvent. To enhance the solubility of the therapeutic agent in the dosage form and/or to improve drug permeation across the skin, co-solvents may be used, E.g., alcohol, glycerol, PG, PEG 400, etc.

Inclusion of buffers: Buffers may be involved in aqueous and hydroalcoholic-based gels to control the pH of the formulation. The solubility of buffer salts is reduced in hydroalcoholic-based vehicles. E.g., Phosphate, citrate, etc.

Preservatives: Certain preservatives cooperate with the hydrophilic polymers used to prepare gels, thereby reducing the concentration of free (antimicrobially active) preservative in the preparation. Therefore, to compensate for this, the initial concentration of these preservatives should be improved. E.g., Parabens, phenolics, etc.

Antioxidants: It may be involved in the formulation to improve the chemical stability of therapeutic agents that are prone to oxidative degradation. Its choice is based on the nature of the vehicle used in the preparation of gel. Water-soluble antioxidants are generally used as the majority of gels are aqueous-based. E.g., Sodium metabisulphite, sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate, etc.

Flavors/Sweetening agents : Flavors and sweetening agents are only incorporated in gels that are designed for administration into the oral cavity (E.g., for the treatment of infection, inflammation, ulceration, etc.).

Sweeteners: Sucrose, liquid glucose, glycerol, sorbitol, saccharin sodium, aspartame, etc.

Flavors: Butterscotch, apricot, peach, vanilla, wintergreen mint, cherry, mint, anise, citrus flavors, raspberry.

Generally the water soluble excipients are firstly dissolved in vehicle, in a mixing vessel by using mechanical stirrer. To prevent aggregation, add hydrophilic polymer to the stirred mixture slowly. Stirring is continued until the dissolution of the polymer has occurred. The excessive stirring results in entrapment of air. The mixing rate must not be extreme or a mixing vessel may be used to which a vacuum may be pulled, to prevent the entrapment of air.⁽²⁴⁾

Characterization studies of Invasomal gels :

- **Entrapment efficiency:** The centrifugation and ultracentrifugation methods determine the entrapment efficiency. A UV spectrophotometer was used to measure the drug concentration at 260 nm.
- **Measurement of viscosity:** Viscosity is measured using a Brookfield viscometer with spindle number 63 and an ideal speed of 10 rpm.
- **Vesicle size:** The average size of prepared invasomes was determined through microscopic vortexing analysis.
- **pH Measurement:** A digital pH meter is used to determine it. 9.2 is the ideal pH.
- **Drug Content:** 20 milliliters of methanol and 100 milligrams of invasomal formulation filtered through Whatmann filter paper.
- **Extrudability Study:** It is based on the amount of formulation that is extruded from a collapsible tube when a load is applied.

- **Spreadability:** $S = ML / T$ where L is the length of the glass slide, T is time in seconds, S is spreadability, and M is weight attached to the upper glass plate.
- **Homogeneity Invasome:** It was assessed visually by looking for aggregates and their appearance.
- **Zeta potential determination:** Malvern zeta sizer with an electric field of 15.24v/cm.⁽²⁵⁾

Skin Permeation Studies for gel preparation:

According to the literature review, a variety of skin types have been used for permeation studies, including human (female) abdominal skin obtained after plastic surgery⁽²⁶⁾, albino (male) Wistar rat skin^(14,27), porcine skin and rabbit skin after the fatty tissue was removed⁽²⁷⁾. Additionally, the diffusion studies were conducted using Franz diffusion cells and pH7.4 PBS was present in the receptor compartment⁽¹⁴⁾. The ability of an invasomal formulation to penetrate the skin can be assessed using confocal laser scanning microscopy⁽²⁸⁾. Interestingly, these investigations verified that nano-invasomes can readily penetrate the skin⁽¹⁴⁾. Additionally, the invasomes can mix with the skin's lipids and change the distribution of SC, which causes the tight lipid junctions to loosen⁽²⁹⁾. The highest level of temoprofin penetration was obtained by the authors. Using 1% w/v citral-based invasomes, the authors achieved the highest level of temoprofin penetration when compared to cineole and a combination of both⁽³⁰⁾. On the other hand, compared to vesicles without terpenes, tolterodine tartrate injections containing 1% terpenes showed improved skin penetration and accumulation⁽²⁷⁾.

Stability Studies:

By employing DLS to measure the change in invasome vesicle size and PDI, one may assess the stability of invasomal dispersion, gel and suspension. We can use SEM, TEM or other suitable methods to confirm the invasomal formulation's shape based on stability studies. The zeta potential of invasomal vesicles can be used to calculate the particle-containing charge changes⁽³¹⁾. The finasteride invasomes were first put through a 120-day stability trial at 4°C and 25°C. After 120 days, it was shown that the entrapment efficiency and zeta potential of vesicles kept at 4°C did not differ significantly from the first assessment; however, at 25°C, there was a significant change in the outcome. In summary, the physical instability of invasome vesicles held at 25 °C resulted in a decrease in entrapment efficiency due to a decrease in negative surface charge caused by the aggregation of invasome vesicles. Consequently, it was noted that the ideal temperature for storing invasomes is 4°C⁽³²⁾. According to the stability profile of tolterodine tartrate invasome, the formulation should be stored at $4 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ rather than 30 °C to prevent significant drug loss⁽²⁷⁾. In conclusion, storing the invasomal formulation under refrigeration may make it more stable.

Storage Conditions:

To avoid deterioration, invasomes should be kept in a dry, cool atmosphere. They are frequently kept in a refrigerator between 2 and 8°C. They should be shielded from light and moisture because these elements can compromise their stability. To reduce their exposure to oxygen, invasomes should be kept in airtight containers

Current innovative formulation in Invasomal drug delivery system:

- ✓ **Ahhmed O.A *et al*** discussed that a new FDA-approved selective size of 109.92 nm and an entrapment efficiency of 96.98% was evaluated for both its phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitor called Avanafil (AVA) is used to treat erectile dysfunction orally. Therefore, the goal of this work was to design optimal nanosized AVA invasomes with improved transdermal administration in order to overcome the aforementioned difficulties. In order to investigate the effects of the following formulation elements on vesicle size (Y1) and entrapment efficiency (Y2), AVA invasomes were created using a Box-Behnken experimental design: phospholipid % (X1), ethanol % (X2), terpene % (X3) and terpene type (X4). After being integrated into a transdermal film made of hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose, the improved formulation which had a vesicular in vivo and ex vivo permeation behaviour in rats. In comparison to the raw AVA film, the optimized AVA invasomal film demonstrated improved ex vivo permeability with an enhancement factor of 2.514 and a more than four-fold improvement in relative bioavailability. These findings shed light on the optimized invasomal film's potential to improve AVA's transdermal penetration and bioavailability.⁽³³⁾
- ✓ **Sanket M. Shah *et al*** evaluates the capacity of three vesicular systems—conventional liposomes, cationic LeciPlex and invasomes—to carry medications deeply into the skin. The ability of the three vesicular systems to penetrate the skin was investigated for two medications: azelaic acid (antiacne) and idebenone (antioxidant/anticancer). To learn more about the variations in the penetrating behavior of the three vesicular systems on excised human skin, an ex vivo investigation was conducted using a fluorescent dye (DiI). LeciPlex formulations demonstrated the effectiveness when loaded with idebenone, followed by invasomes and liposomes, according to in vitro cytotoxicity experiments on B16F10 melanoma cell lines. High antibacterial activity was shown for DDAB leciplex, followed by about similar activity for invasomes and CTAB LeciPlex, followed by liposomes, in an in vitro antimicrobial evaluation of azelaic acid-loaded systems on *Propionibacterium acne*. Invasomes showed the strongest antiacne efficacy in a trial of azelaic acid-loaded systems in rats, followed by liposomes and LeciPlex.⁽³⁴⁾
- ✓ **Duangjit *et al*** examined the creation of several vesicle compositions for curcumin transdermal administration. Techniques: A sonication technique was used to create curcumin-loaded vesicles that included a regulated quantity of phospholipid, cholesterol, curcumin, and different concentrations of penetration enhancers (Tween 20 and terpene). The impact of penetration enhancers on the intercellular lipid microstructure was further assessed using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Outcomes: All formulations had vesicles that were smaller than 50

nm, had a limited size range and had a negative zeta potential. The DSC thermogram and FTIR spectra suggested that the penetration enhancers may cause the skin to become more fluid.⁽³⁵⁾

- ✓ **Dragicevic-curic.N et al** explains about the topical photodynamic treatment (PDT) with a formulation containing temoporfin (mTHPC) would be beneficial for cutaneous malignant or non-malignant illnesses. The goal of this work was to examine the photodynamic efficacy of mTHPC-loaded invasomes in vitro using two cell lines: the epidermoid tumor cell line A431 and the human colorectal tumor cell line HT29. mTHPC's intracellular location, phototoxicity and dark toxicity were investigated. According to the results, HT29 cells, and particularly A431 cells that were more susceptible to PDT, were able to have their survival rates decreased by mTHPC-invasomes and mTHPC-ethanolic solution applied at a 2 μ M mTHPC concentration and photoirradiation at 20 J/cm². because it illustrates the potential of invasomes for topical PDT of cutaneous malignant disorders.⁽³⁶⁾
- ✓ **Chen.M et al** The goal of the current study is to assess the skin delivery potential of several vesicular systems, such as ethosomes containing ferulic acid (FA), an antioxidant with a broad range of therapeutic effects against different diseases, conventional liposomes (CL), Tween 80based deformable liposomes (DL) and invasomes (INS).These vesicular liposomal systems greatly increased both the drug deposition in skin and the permeation profile of ferulic acid through the human stratum corneum epidermal membrane (SCE), according to in vitro skin permeation and skin deposition assays. The ethosomal system containing 18.0 mg/ml of ferulic acid demonstrated.⁽³⁷⁾
- ✓ **Lakshmi, P et al** Curcumin cyclodextrin complexes were made using the co-precipitation and physical mixing methods. CHL1 and CHL2 formulations were refined for more research. The study discovered that 90% of curcumin was bound by complexation with HP β CD in a 1:2 ratio made using the co-precipitation method. It was discovered that invasomal preparation containing 0.5% limonene and 4% ethanol increased permeability by 8.11 times compared to the control. Ex vivo skin permeation studies of CHL1 using rat abdominal skin revealed cumulative drug permeated (Q₂₄) of 70.32 μ g/cm², steady state transdermal flux of 3.344 μ g/cm²/hr-1, permeability coefficient of 5.35 cm/hr, and lag time of 1 hour when compared with control formulation. In vivo diffusion studies were carried out using Franz diffusion cell. According to the findings, curcumin's solubility was enhanced by complexing with HP β CD, and its skin penetration was enhanced by invasomal preparation with 0.5% limonene.⁽³⁸⁾
- ✓ **Dragicevic-curic.N et al** One extremely powerful second-generation synthetic photosensitizer is temoporfin (mTHPC). It has demonstrated efficacy in the treatment of primary non-melanomatous tumors of the head and neck area, in the palliative management of refractory oral carcinomas and in the photodynamic therapy of early or recurrent oral carcinomas. This investigation aimed to examine the photodynamic

effectiveness of new mTHPC-loaded invasomes following photoirradiation and topical application into the skin of mice with the subcutaneously implanted human colorectal tumor HT29. As penetration enhancers, invasomes are vesicles that contain phospholipids together with a combination of terpenes (cineole, citral, and d-limonene) or just one terpene (citral) and ethanol.⁽³⁹⁾

- ✓ **B.Kamaleshwari, et al** prepared and evaluated twelve formulations of Mupirocin invasomes, were prepared using a mechanical dispersion method for antibacterial activity. (F5) exhibiting the smallest size (92nm to 1250nm). The poly dispersibility index indicated uniform particle size distribution (0.136-0.624), confirming homogeneous preparation. Formulation F5 showed superior performance with the highest entrapment efficiency (83%) and drug content (90%), indicating efficient encapsulation of mupirocin. In-vitro drug release ranged from 62% to 86% over 30 hours and followed first-order release kinetics. Antibacterial studies against *Staphylococcus aureus* revealed variation among formulations, with zones of inhibition ranging from 10 mm to 20 mm; formulation F2 exhibited the maximum activity, while F10 showed the least. Stability studies confirmed that formulation F5 remained stable and retained its performance over a period of three months. Overall, mupirocin-loaded invasomes, particularly formulation F5, demonstrate significant potential for topical management of bacterial skin infections due to their sustained drug release, improved skin penetration, and effective antibacterial activity.⁽³⁾
- ✓ **Shailaja, et al** Prepared and evaluated twelve formulation of naproxen sodium loaded invasomes were prepared by thin film hydration technique for topical application. All the formulations were evaluated for drug content, entrapment efficiency, particle size, zeta potential, and invitro drug release. Among the twelve formulations of invasomes, the INV2 formulation (1:1) ratio containing 40mg drug and 40mg surfactant (span60) was found to be the best formulation with a drug content of 96.62%, entrapment efficiency of 90.9%, zeta potential of -68.5mV, mean particle diameter of 572.4 nm, and *in vitro* drug release of 91.6% in a time period of 12 hrs and followed the zero order kinetics with non fickian diffusion mechanism.⁽⁴⁰⁾
- ✓ **Sharma, et al** developed and evaluated a six formulation of Tazarotene -loaded invasomal drug carrier systems for topical disease. Evaluated for average vesicle size, zeta potential and entrapment efficiency. Drug content of Tazarotene incorporated invasomes gel for formulation TIG-1, TIG-2 and TIG-3 was found to be 97.8540.32, 99.12±0.25 and 98.7440.14 respectively. The maximum drug content was found in formulation TIG-2 (99.1240.25), select as optimized formulation. When the regression coefficient values of were compared, it was observed that '12' values of Higuchi was maximum Le.0.994 hence indicating drug release from formulations was found to follow Higuchi kinetics.⁽⁴¹⁾
- ✓ **Annapurna Tiwari, et al** formulated and evaluated six formulations of Acyclovir loaded in to invasomes by mechanical dispersion technique for Topical disease treatment. The

maximum drug content was found in formulation TIG2 (99.12 ± 0.25) and selected as optimized formulation. When the regression coefficient values were compared, it was observed that '12' values of higuchi was maximum 0.994 hence indicating drug release from formulations was found to follow higuchi release kinetic.⁽⁴²⁾

- ✓ **Pawan Singh, et al** prepared and evaluated six formulation of Luliconazole loaded invasomes by mechanical dispersion technique for fungal infections. The maximum drug content was found in formulation LG-2 (99.12 ± 0.25) and selected as optimized formulation. When the regression coefficient values were compared, it was observed that '12' values of higuchi was maximum i.c.0.995 hence indicating drug release from formulations was found to follow higuchi release kinetic.⁽⁴³⁾

- ✓ **Moguloori Sai Sowmys, et al** prepared and evaluated these formulation of diclofenac sodium invasomes by thin film hydration technique. F1 Formulation prepared try using 1:1 ratio of drug and lipid at 400 rpm was showing promising results with drug content as 32.51% and drug release of 72.48% were able to sustain the drug release for 12 hours This study was performed to determine parameters such as drug content and drug release. Fi formulation was considered as the best formulation as it shown best and promising results.⁽⁴⁴⁾

Conclusion

The review providing valuable literature in invasomal gel, structure and composition of invasomes, characterization studies of invasomal gel and their currently applied formulation in transdermal drug delivery system. Therefore, with promising further optimization and large-scale development, invasomal gels are expected to have a greater clinical and pharmaceutical impact in the future formulations compared to traditional gel formulations.

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